

ACADEMIC MOBILITY OF TEACHERS AS A TOOL FOR THE INTERNATIONALIZATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION

Ahmedova P. A.

Senior Lecturer, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages,
Uzbekistan

Wang Xiaoxu

Lecturer, Weinan Normal University, PRC (China)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18281429>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th January 2026

Accepted: 16th January 2026

Online: 17th January 2026

KEYWORDS

academic mobility of teachers; internationalization of higher education; teacher education; Sino-Uzbek cooperation; Russian as a foreign language; intercultural communication; student mobility; international academic cooperation

ABSTRACT

The article examines academic mobility of teachers as a tool for the internationalization of higher education in the context of Sino-Uzbek cooperation. The purpose of the study is to analyze the pedagogical and institutional effects of short-term academic mobility of teachers at pedagogical universities. The methodological framework of the research is based on a qualitative case study approach, including participant observation, analysis of classroom teaching, methodological activities, and academic supervision of students. The empirical basis of the study is the experience of academic mobility of teachers from Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages at Weinan Normal University (PRC).

The findings demonstrate that substantively structured academic mobility of teachers contributes to the transfer of pedagogical practices, the development of students' intercultural communicative competence, and the formation of sustainable professional links between partner universities. It is shown that teacher mobility can function as a catalyst for institutional forms of internationalization, including the initiation of student mobility. In particular, as a result of the implemented program, two students of a Chinese pedagogical university are currently participating in an exchange program at an Uzbek higher education institution, which indicates a transition of academic interaction into a sustainable phase.

The scientific novelty of the study lies in the analysis of short-term academic mobility of teachers as a system-forming element of the internationalization of pedagogical universities. The practical significance of the research consists in the possibility of applying the presented conclusions in the design of academic mobility programs oriented toward language and teacher education..

In recent decades, the internationalization of higher education has been regarded as one of the key factors enhancing the quality of university education and its competitiveness within the global academic space. In academic research, internationalization is interpreted as a complex and multi-level process encompassing academic mobility, transnational educational programs, international research cooperation, and the development of intercultural communication within the university environment [Knight, 2004; Altbach, Knight, 2007]. In this context, academic mobility functions not only as a form of academic exchange but also as an instrument of institutional development influencing the content of educational programs and the professional practices of university teachers.

Despite sustained scholarly interest in academic mobility, the majority of studies focus predominantly on student exchanges as the most widespread and formalized form of international interaction [Teichler, 2004; OECD, 2019]. Academic mobility of teachers, especially in short-term formats, has far less frequently become an object of independent analysis and is often treated as an auxiliary component of internationalization. At the same time, a number of studies emphasize that teachers act as key agents in the transfer of academic norms, pedagogical approaches, and research practices between universities [Altbach, 2016].

Teacher mobility acquires particular significance within the system of teacher education, where internationalization is directly linked to the preparation of future teachers and foreign language instructors. Under such institutional conditions, teacher mobility performs a dual function: on the one hand, it contributes to the professional development of the participants themselves; on the other hand, it exerts an indirect influence on students' educational trajectories and the overall quality of the learning process. As noted by J. Knight, sustainable forms of internationalization emerge not through isolated activities, but through the long-term involvement of academic staff in institutional processes [Knight, 2004].

In recent years, educational cooperation between the People's Republic of China and the countries of Central Asia has demonstrated a stable dynamic of development. The Chinese model of higher education internationalization is oriented toward expanding international academic links, attracting foreign faculty members, and developing humanitarian cooperation, including in the field of teacher education [Zha, 2016; Yang, 2015]. For Uzbek universities, participation in such programs has strategic importance, as it enables the integration of international experience into the national system of training specialists in foreign languages and intercultural communication.

At the same time, the analysis of the practical outcomes of academic mobility of teachers in the context of Sino-Uzbek cooperation remains insufficiently represented in academic literature. In most cases, publications are limited to descriptions of internship programs or reports on international visits, without addressing their institutional effects or their influence on the development of sustainable forms of academic exchange. This situation necessitates the examination of empirical cases that allow tracing how short-term teacher mobility may be transformed into broader forms of higher education internationalization.

The present study is devoted to the analysis of academic mobility of teachers from Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages at Weinan Normal University as a tool for the internationalization of higher education. The focus is placed not on the mere fact of the

academic visit, but on its substantive content and institutional outcomes, including the development of pedagogical interaction, scientific and methodological exchange, and the initiation of student mobility. This approach makes it possible to consider teacher academic mobility not as an episodic professional event, but as a mechanism for forming sustainable international cooperation between pedagogical universities.

The purpose of the study is to analyze academic mobility of teachers as a factor in the internationalization of higher education within the framework of Sino-Uzbek cooperation. The research seeks to identify the pedagogical and institutional effects of short-term mobility and to determine its potential for developing student exchanges and long-term forms of academic partnership.

The methodological logic of the research is based on a qualitative approach oriented toward the analysis of a specific institutional case. The choice of a case study method is обусловлена the need to identify not quantitative indicators of academic mobility, but its substantive characteristics and mechanisms of influence on the educational process and international cooperation. Qualitative methods make it possible to capture complex interrelations between pedagogical practice, intercultural interaction, and institutional outcomes of academic exchange, which corresponds to the objectives of the present study [Teichler, 2004].

The methodological framework of the research presupposed the analysis of teacher academic mobility not as a set of isolated activities, but as an integral process of professional and institutional interaction. Particular attention was paid to the forms of teachers' involvement in the educational and scientific-methodological activities of the host university, as well as to the outcomes emerging in the course of such interaction. Empirical data were collected through participant observation, analysis of classroom teaching, methodological events, and academic supervision of students, which made it possible to identify both pedagogical and institutional effects of academic mobility. This approach is consistent with the positions of researchers emphasizing the importance of qualitative methods in the study of higher education internationalization, especially in the context of pedagogical universities and language education [Teichler, 2004; Knight, 2004].

The analysis of educational interaction revealed that one of the key outcomes of academic mobility was a qualitative expansion of the pedagogical toolkit used in teaching Russian as a foreign language. Classroom instruction at the host university was oriented toward a communicative model of teaching, which presupposes active student engagement in speech activities and the use of language in simulated real-life communication situations. The application of role plays, situational dialogues, and problem-based tasks made it possible not only to activate students' oral speech, but also to identify the specifics of their linguistic interference, which is of fundamental importance for the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language in a Chinese classroom [Azimov, Shchukin, 2017].

Special attention during the classes was paid to the cultural and sociolinguistic context, since the formation of communicative competence is impossible without consideration of learners' national and cultural characteristics. The adaptation of instructional materials to the Chinese audience was reflected in the selection of lexical topics, the use of visual supports, and the gradual increase in the complexity of speech tasks. The observations obtained confirm

the thesis that a teacher participating in academic mobility acts not only as a carrier of professional knowledge, but also as a mediator of intercultural communication capable of adapting methodological solutions to a different educational environment [Passov, 2016; Leontiev, 2019].

A significant component of academic mobility was teachers' participation in methodological seminars and professional discussions devoted to contemporary approaches to teaching and assessment in foreign language education. The discussions addressed issues of formative assessment, the use of portfolios, and the application of gamification elements in the educational process. A comparison of methodological approaches demonstrated that, despite differences in the organization of the educational process and forms of assessment in pedagogical universities in China and Uzbekistan, there is a shared orientation toward increasing the practical relevance of instruction and developing student autonomy. This conclusion is consistent with the results of international studies indicating the convergence of pedagogical models under conditions of higher education internationalization [OECD, 2019].

Particular attention should be paid to the experience of academic supervision of undergraduate thesis projects of senior students. This form of academic interaction made it possible to identify the specifics of organizing research activities at the host university and to compare requirements for the structure and methodological justification of graduation theses. During the supervision process, emphasis was placed on developing students' skills in problem formulation, argumentation, and logical presentation of research results. Analysis of this experience shows that the involvement of foreign teachers in supervising graduation projects contributes to broadening students' academic horizons and shaping their understanding of international standards of academic writing, as previously noted in studies on the internationalization of teacher education [Altbach, 2016].

Taken together, the above-mentioned forms of academic interaction contributed to the formation of sustainable professional contacts between teachers of the two universities. Unlike formal academic visits primarily oriented toward introductory activities, the mobility under consideration was aimed at substantive cooperation and joint professional activity. This created a basis for a transition from individual experience exchange to institutionally significant forms of interaction, which is regarded in academic literature as one of the key indicators of effective internationalization [Knight, 2004; Zha, 2016].

The most illustrative institutional outcome of academic mobility manifested itself in the development of student exchange between partner universities. As a result of the academic visit, an agreement was reached on sending students for exchange studies, and currently two students from Weinan Normal University are studying at Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages. This fact should be interpreted not so much as a quantitative indicator, but rather as evidence of a transition of cooperation into a sustainable phase. Even a limited number of participants at the initial stage reflects the institutionalization of academic ties and the formation of mechanisms for long-term international interaction, as emphasized in studies on the development of academic mobility in pedagogical universities [Yang, 2015].

Thus, the analysis of empirical material demonstrates that short-term academic mobility of teachers, provided that it is substantively structured and characterized by active involvement in the educational process, is capable of exerting a comprehensive influence on

the internationalization of higher education. The obtained results show that teacher mobility can function not as an auxiliary, but as a system-forming element of international cooperation, ensuring the transfer of pedagogical practices, the development of intercultural academic dialogue, and the initiation of student mobility as one of the key indicators of sustainable internationalization.

The results obtained make it possible to correlate the empirical case with existing theoretical models of higher education internationalization and to refine several propositions presented in academic literature. In the works of P. Altbach and J. Knight, internationalization is viewed as a systemic process involving not only the formal expansion of international contacts, but also the transformation of internal academic practices of universities [Knight, 2004; Altbach, Knight, 2007]. The analysis of the implemented academic mobility program confirms this position and demonstrates that the substantive involvement of teachers in the educational and scientific-methodological processes of the host university is a key condition for the emergence of sustainable institutional effects.

In contrast to models of academic mobility primarily oriented toward quantitative indicators, the case under consideration illustrates the qualitative dimension of internationalization. Teacher mobility in this context was not limited to the transmission of experience or familiarization with educational infrastructure, but functioned as a mechanism of joint professional action, within which pedagogical approaches were exchanged, academic expectations were aligned, and trust-based professional relationships were formed. This format of interaction corresponds to the approach according to which internationalization is realized through the “embeddedness” of the international component in the everyday academic practice of the university [Teichler, 2004].

The results of the study acquire particular significance in the context of teacher and language education. As research in foreign language teaching methodology shows, the effectiveness of internationalization largely depends on teachers’ ability to adapt methodological solutions to a different cultural and educational environment [Passov, 2016; Azimov, Shchukin, 2017]. The analysis of classroom instruction and methodological seminars conducted within the framework of academic mobility confirms that teachers in conditions of international interaction perform the function of mediators between different pedagogical traditions. This not only expands their professional toolkit, but also shapes students’ understanding of the diversity of academic cultures and approaches to learning.

The institutional effect of academic mobility was most clearly manifested in the initiation of student exchange between partner universities. From the perspective of internationalization theory, this outcome is of particular interest, as it demonstrates a transition from individual professional interaction to a sustainable form of inter-university cooperation. Academic literature emphasizes that student mobility emerging as a continuation of teacher exchanges is an indicator of a high level of trust between educational institutions and evidence of the alignment of academic standards [Altbach, 2016; Zha, 2016]. In the present case, the exchange study of two students should be interpreted not as an isolated fact, but as an indicator of the institutionalization of academic ties.

It is important to emphasize that quantitative parameters of student mobility at the initial stage are not decisive. As noted by R. Yang, small-scale but substantively well-

structured forms of international cooperation are capable of evolving over time into sustainable educational trajectories and expanded academic exchange programs [Yang, 2015]. From this perspective, the presented case illustrates the potential of short-term academic mobility of teachers as a trigger for long-term internationalization processes, especially in pedagogical universities, where international activities often develop gradually and require institutional “maturation.”

The discussion of results also allows for a clarification of the role of teachers within the system of international university cooperation. Unlike administrative mechanisms of internationalization, teacher mobility relies on the professional autonomy and personal academic responsibility of participants, which makes it particularly sensitive to the content and quality of implemented forms of interaction. The experience under consideration demonstrates that, given institutional support and clearly defined academic objectives, teachers are capable of acting as active agents of internationalization, influencing both the educational process and the strategic development of inter-university relations.

Overall, the obtained data allow academic mobility of teachers to be regarded as a multifunctional instrument of higher education internationalization combining pedagogical, scientific, and institutional dimensions. The presented empirical material complements existing theoretical models by emphasizing the role of short-term but substantively intensive forms of mobility in the development of sustainable international cooperation.

In conclusion, the study confirms the high significance of teacher academic mobility for the internationalization of pedagogical universities. The implemented case of Sino-Uzbek cooperation demonstrates that even time-limited mobility programs may lead to long-term outcomes provided that they are integrated into the educational and scientific-methodological context of the host university. The practical significance of the research lies in the possibility of applying the obtained conclusions in the design of academic mobility programs oriented toward language and teacher education.

Prospects for further research are associated with the analysis of long-term academic trajectories of students participating in exchange programs, as well as with the exploration of opportunities for expanding cooperation in the format of joint educational programs and research projects. In addition, comparative studies aimed at identifying the specific features of teacher academic mobility in different regional and institutional contexts appear to be promising.

The conducted research confirms that academic mobility of teachers may be regarded as an effective instrument of higher education internationalization, provided that it is substantively structured and institutionally supported. The analysis of the experience of Sino-Uzbek cooperation in the field of teacher education shows that short-term academic visits oriented toward the active involvement of teachers in the educational and scientific-methodological processes of the host university are capable of exerting a comprehensive influence on the development of international academic relations.

The obtained results indicate that teacher mobility transcends the level of individual professional exchange and acquires clear institutional significance. Teachers’ participation in classroom instruction, methodological seminars, and academic supervision of students contributes to the transfer of pedagogical practices, the alignment of academic standards, and

the formation of sustainable professional contacts between partner universities. In this context, teachers act as key agents of internationalization, ensuring the integration of international components into everyday educational practice.

A particularly significant outcome of the implemented program was the development of student mobility as a continuation of teacher academic exchange. The fact that two students from Weinan Normal University are currently studying at Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages should be regarded not as an isolated quantitative indicator, but as evidence of the institutionalization of academic cooperation. This result confirms that substantively structured academic mobility of teachers can serve as a catalyst for broader internationalization processes, including student mobility and the expansion of inter-university cooperation formats.

The practical significance of the study lies in the possibility of using the presented case in the development and implementation of academic mobility programs oriented toward pedagogical universities and language education. The conclusions obtained may be applied in the design of short-term mobility programs aimed not only at experience exchange, but also at achieving long-term institutional outcomes.

Future research perspectives are associated with analyzing the sustainability of the identified effects of academic mobility, examining the academic trajectories of students participating in exchange programs, and expanding the empirical base through the inclusion of comparable cases from other regions and institutional contexts. This will allow for a deeper understanding of the role of teacher mobility in the system of higher education internationalization and for refining the mechanisms of its influence on the development of international academic cooperation.

References:

1. Altbach, P. G. *Global Perspectives on Higher Education*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 2016. 332 p.
2. Altbach, P. G., & Knight, J. The internationalization of higher education. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 2007, Vol. 11, No. 3-4, pp. 290-305. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315307303542>
3. Knight, J. Internationalization remodeled: Definition, approaches, and rationales. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 2004, Vol. 8, No. 1, pp. 5-31. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315303260832>
4. Teichler, U. Internationalisation of higher education. *European Journal of Education*, 2004, Vol. 39, No. 1, pp. 93-106. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1465-3435.2004.00164.x>
5. OECD. *Education at a Glance 2019: OECD Indicators*. Paris: OECD Publishing, 2019.
6. Zha, Q. Internationalization of higher education in China. In: *Spotlight on China*. Dordrecht: Springer, 2016, pp. 35-49. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6300-669-9_3
7. Yang, R. *Repositioning Chinese Higher Education*. Rotterdam: Sense Publishers, 2015.
8. Bolotov, V. A. *Teacher Education in the Context of Globalization*. Moscow, 2018. (in Russian)
9. Frolov, Yu. V. *Internationalization of Higher Education: Strategies and Practices*. Moscow, 2020. (in Russian)

10. Azimov, E. G., & Shchukin, A. N. *Methods of Teaching Russian as a Foreign Language*. Moscow, 2017. (in Russian)
11. Passov, E. I. *The Communicative Method of Teaching Foreign Language Speaking*. Moscow, 2016. (in Russian)
12. Leontiyev, A. A. *Language, Speech, and Speech Activity*. Moscow, 2019. (in Russian)

